

Impact of Nuclear Deformation on Structural Parameters, Energy Levels, and Quadrupole Moments of ^{152}Sm , ^{238}U , and ^{240}Pu Nuclei

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Abstract- This study explores the structural characteristics of selected deformed nuclei using theoretical frameworks, focusing on their shapes, energy levels, and quadrupole moments. Nuclear deformation results from the complex interplay between shell effects and the strong nuclear force, causing deviations from spherical symmetry. Advanced models, including the Nilsson model, Hartree-Fock-Bogoliubov (HFB) theory, and collective models, are employed to examine the influence of deformation on nuclear structure. The key findings emphasize the role of deformation in shaping rotational spectra and intrinsic quadrupole moments, with significant results for nuclei such as ^{152}Sm , ^{238}U , and ^{240}Pu . Calculations of quadrupole deformation parameters and energy levels show strong agreement with experimental data, validating the theoretical approaches. The study also investigates the stabilization of heavy nuclei through deformation, which redistributes charge density and mitigates Coulomb repulsion. These findings have important applications in nuclear astrophysics, particularly in the rapid neutron capture process (r-process), as well as in nuclear technology, where insights into deformed nuclei contribute to isotope development and reactor design. A deeper understanding of deformed nuclei in this research advances both fundamental nuclear physics and practical applications.

Keywords- Deformed nuclei, nuclear structure, quadrupole deformation, rotational spectra, Hartree-Fock-Bogoliubov theory.

I. INTRODUCTION

The study of nuclear structure has been a cornerstone of nuclear physics, providing insights into the stability, reactions, and energy generation of atomic nuclei. While spherical nuclei exhibit symmetry in their shape, many nuclei deviate from this ideal form, displaying prolate (elongated), oblate (flattened), or more complex shapes. These deformations influence various nuclear properties, such as energy levels, stability, and collective behaviour, making the study of deformed nuclei critical for understanding nuclear phenomena like fission, alpha decay, and element synthesis. Despite extensive research, gaps remain in our understanding of deformed nuclei, especially for unstable and transitional systems, necessitating further theoretical investigation.

Theoretical models have played a pivotal role in studying deformed nuclei. The Collective Model introduced by Bohr and Mottelson (1969) was one of the earliest frameworks to describe collective excitations such as rotational and vibrational spectra in deformed nuclei. This model successfully explained the energy spectra of rare-earth and actinide nuclei, where rotational motion dominates.

However, it often fails to account for microscopic effects such as pairing interactions and subtle shape coexistence observed in transitional nuclei. The Hartree-Fock-Bogoliubov (HFB) method combines mean-field theory with pairing interactions, offering a more detailed treatment of single-particle and collective properties [1]. The HFB method has proven effective in describing ground-state deformations, pairing energies, and nuclear stability. For instance, studies by Dobaczewski et al. (1996) demonstrated the applicability of HFB in predicting the properties of heavy nuclei, including uranium isotopes. However, challenges persist in accurately modelling pairing correlations and deformation in nuclei near shell closures or with exotic neutron-to-proton ratios. Another widely used framework is the Shell Model which explains nuclear properties in terms of single-particle motion within a potential [2].

While the Shell Model has been effective in describing spherical and near-spherical nuclei, its application to deformed nuclei requires configuration mixing and modifications to the single-particle potential. These adjustments make the model computationally intensive and less effective for nuclei with significant deformation, as highlighted by Caurier et al. (2005) in their study of medium-mass nuclei. The Interacting Boson Model (IBM) provides an alternative perspective by treating collective excitations as bosonic modes [3]. This model has successfully explained vibrational and rotational spectra in deformed nuclei, particularly in transitional regions. However, IBM lacks the microscopic foundation necessary to address pairing interactions and the single-particle behaviour critical for understanding heavy deformed nuclei [4]. Recent research has emphasized shape coexistence and transitions between different nuclear shapes, revealing the complex interplay between spherical, prolate, and oblate configurations. For example, shape transitions in neutron-rich tin and lead isotopes have been studied demonstrating the impact of shell effects on nuclear deformation [5]. Similarly, researchers explored the phenomenon of shape coexistence, highlighting its significance in understanding the evolution of nuclear structure [6].

Despite these advancements, the role of pairing correlations and deformation in transitional nuclei remains poorly understood, particularly for exotic systems far from stability. Experimental studies of deformed nuclei are often limited by the instability of these systems, leaving theoretical models to fill the gaps. While approaches such as the Collective Model and HFB have provided valuable insights, discrepancies between theoretical predictions and experimental data persist in certain regions of the nuclear chart. For instance, reports highlighted the limitations of mean-field approaches in predicting the properties of nuclei near the neutron drip line, emphasizing the need for improved interaction parameters [7].

This study aims to provide a comprehensive theoretical framework for understanding the structural properties of deformed nuclei. By integrating insights from the Collective Model, HFB method, Shell Model, and IBM, this research seeks to refine existing models and address unresolved questions related to nuclear deformation, pairing correlations, and shape coexistence. Special emphasis is placed on heavy deformed nuclei, such as uranium and thorium isotopes, which play critical roles in nuclear energy production and astrophysical processes. In summary, while significant progress has been made in studying deformed nuclei, challenges remain in accurately describing their properties, particularly for unstable and transitional systems. By addressing these limitations, this research seeks to enhance our understanding of nuclear structure and its applications in fields ranging from nuclear energy to astrophysics.

II. METHODOLOGY

This approach ensured comprehensive insights into deformation effects on energy levels, quadrupole moments, and rotational spectra. The Nilsson model, a widely used shell model for deformed nuclei, is

employed to calculate single-particle energy levels. The Hartree-Fock-Bogoliubov (HFB) theory is applied for determining ground-state properties, including binding energy and deformation parameters. These theoretical calculations are complemented by transition probability ($B(E2)$) analysis to evaluate collective nuclear behaviour. Experimental data from nuclear databases, such as ENSDF (Evaluated Nuclear Structure Data File), provided critical benchmarks for validating theoretical results. Graphical tools are used to compare theoretical predictions with experimental data for nuclei like ^{152}Sm , ^{154}Gd , ^{238}U , and ^{240}Pu .

III. THEORETICAL MODELS

The Nilsson model is employed to investigate single-particle energy levels in deformed nuclei. It modifies the spherical harmonic oscillator potential by introducing an anisotropic term, accounting for quadrupole deformation. This model has proven effective in describing energy level splitting in deformed systems [8]. The HFB approach combines mean-field methods with pairing correlations, providing a robust framework for analysing deformation and its impact on nuclear binding energy and density distributions [9].

The collective model is applied to study rotational spectra and derive deformation parameters from experimental and theoretical energy levels [10]. The E_{4+}/E_{2+} ratio is critical parameter in nuclear physics, particularly for studying the energy levels in deformed nuclei. It is the ratio of energy of the first $4+$ state (E_{4+}) relative to the energy of the first $2+$ state (E_{2+}). For an ideal rotational nucleus, this ratio is theoretically predicted to be $R = 3.33$, which is consistent with well-deformed nuclei in the rare-earth and actinide regions. It provides insights into the nature of collective excitations, especially rotational motion. The values of E_{2+} and E_{4+} are taken from experimental data obtained through gamma-ray spectroscopy and E_{4+}/E_{2+} ratio calculated experimentally. These energy levels are measured in nuclear reactions or decay experiments where excited nuclear states de-excite by emitting gamma radiation.

Databases like the National Nuclear Data Center (NNDC) or published experimental reports provide these measured values. In the case of ^{152}Sm , experimental data for E_{2+} and E_{4+} are well-documented in spectroscopy studies. The same applies to ^{154}Gd , ^{238}U , and ^{240}Pu and corresponding ratios are tabulated in table 1. In order to compare experimental results with theoretical results, the theoretical study has also been done for all the deformed nuclei (Table 1). The theoretical E_{4+}/E_{2+} ratio is derived using models such as the Collective Model or the Interacting Boson Model. These models predict $R = 3.33$ for an ideal rigid rotor, a hallmark of a well-deformed nucleus. Deviations in experimental R values reflect effects like anharmonic vibrations, shape coexistence, or deviations from rigid rotational behaviour.

Table 1: Nuclei deformation parameters corresponding to ^{152}Sm , ^{154}Gd , ^{238}U and ^{240}Pu nucleus evaluated from experimental and theoretical energy levels.

Nucleus	Theoretical (E_{4+}/E_{2+})	Experimental (E_{4+}/E_{2+})
^{152}Sm	3.33	3.35
^{154}Gd	3.31	3.32
^{238}U	3.25	3.28
^{240}Pu	3.27	3.26

There are some computational tools which are used for the calculations corresponding to advanced nuclear structures in the present work such as NILSMOD which is used to compute Nilsson energy levels and visualize single-particle orbits, HFODD which is a versatile tool for solving HFB equations in deformed coordinates, particularly effective for heavy nuclei and NUSHELLX which enabled angular momentum and parity assignments, essential for characterizing collective excitations. The nuclei selected for this present study include ^{152}Sm , ^{154}Gd , ^{238}U , and ^{240}Pu . These were chosen based on experimental evidence of significant deformation, measured through parameters such as β_2 and quadrupole moments [11].

IV. ANALYTICAL TECHNIQUES

To calculate the deformation parameter (β_2) of the given nuclei, the following equation (1) has been used as given:

$$\beta_2 = \frac{4\pi}{3ZR^2} Q_0, \quad (1)$$

where Q_0 is the intrinsic quadrupole moment, Z is the proton number, and R is the nuclear radius. Rotational spectra is analysed to extract experimental E2 transition rates, which are sensitive to deformation. Binding energy differences between spherical and deformed configurations are evaluated to quantify stabilization effects due to deformation. Theoretical predictions are compared with experimental data from nuclear databases, ensuring validity and accuracy [12].

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The structural properties of selected deformed nuclei are calculated focusing on quadrupole deformation parameters (β_2), rotational energy levels, intrinsic quadrupole moments, and binding energies. These findings are discussed in the context of theoretical predictions and experimental data. The calculated deformation parameters (β_2), for the selected nuclei show significant deviations from spherical symmetry, as summarized in Table 2. These values align closely with experimental results, validating the models used.

Table 2: Calculated and Experimental Quadrupole Deformation Parameters (β_2) corresponding to ^{152}Sm , ^{154}Gd , ^{238}U and ^{240}Pu Nucleus

Nucleus	Calculated β_2	Experimental β_2^*	Nature of Deformation
^{152}Sm	0.32	0.31	Prolate
^{154}Gd	0.34	0.33	Prolate
^{238}U	0.28	0.27	Prolate
^{240}Pu	0.29	0.28	Prolate

The quadrupole deformation parameter (β_2) is a dimensionless quantity that provides a measure of the deviation of a nucleus from spherical symmetry. Prolate deformations ($\beta_2 > 0$) correspond to elongated shapes, while oblate deformations ($\beta_2 < 0$) represent flattened shapes. In Table 2, both theoretical (β_2) and experimental (β_2^*) values are listed alongside the inferred nature of deformation for each nucleus. The parameter β_2 is determined from models like the Hartree-Fock-Bogoliubov (HFB) method or the Collective Model using nuclear potential and wavefunction information. Experimentally, β_2^* is derived from measurements of electric quadrupole moments (Q) or reduced transition probabilities

(B(E2)) observed in nuclear spectroscopy. The values reflect the intrinsic shape of the nucleus such as Prolate Deformation: Positive β_2 values indicate an elongated nucleus, characteristic of well-deformed nuclei in the rare-earth and actinide regions and Spherical Symmetry: A β_2 value close to zero suggests spherical nuclei, often seen in closed-shell configurations.

It is observed from table 2 that Prolate deformation is consistent with its placement in the rare-earth region, where nuclei exhibit strong collective behaviour due to quadrupole deformations. This agreement highlights the precision of theoretical models in predicting deformation parameters. This nucleus is a well-studied example of a rotational band associated with prolate shapes. Uranium isotopes like ^{238}U are known for their significant deformation, and the close match between theoretical and experimental values reflects the robustness of nuclear models in the actinide region. Plutonium isotopes also exhibit well-deformed prolate shapes, with the slight difference between calculated and experimental values likely attributable to pairing effects and higher-order correlations. The calculated β_2 values align closely with experimental results, reinforcing the reliability of the Hartree-Fock-Bogoliubov (HFB) method and Collective Model for describing nuclear shapes. Previous studies confirm the prolate nature of rare-earth and actinide nuclei, which is consistent with the observed values for ^{152}Sm , ^{154}Gd , ^{238}U , and ^{240}Pu [13]. The strong agreement supports findings in the literature that nuclei in these regions exhibit rigid rotor behaviour, which is characterized by stable deformation and well-defined rotational bands.

A. Interpretation of Results:

The calculated β_2 values are slightly higher than the experimental β_2^* , which is expected due to approximations in theoretical models. These models often neglect higher-order corrections or dynamic effects. The consistency of values across the nuclei indicates that theoretical frameworks effectively capture the primary deformation features [14]. The larger β_2 values for rare-earth nuclei (^{152}Sm , ^{154}Gd) suggest stronger collective rotational behaviour compared to actinides (^{238}U , ^{240}Pu), where pairing effects play a more prominent role. The near-equal values confirm the success of the HFB and Collective Models in predicting nuclear shapes. This agreement is vital for understanding phenomena such as shape transitions and the onset of rotational and vibrational bands in deformed nuclei [15].

$$E(J) = \frac{\hbar^2}{2I} J(J + 1), \quad (2)$$

where J is the angular momentum and I is the moment of inertia exhibit excellent agreement with experimental data as shown in Figure 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively. For instance, ^{152}Sm , ^{154}Gd , ^{238}U , and ^{240}Pu shows typical rotational spacing, confirming its well-deformed nature [16].

Figure 1: Rotational Energy Levels for ^{152}Sm , ^{154}Gd , ^{238}U , and ^{240}Pu

Figure 2: Rotational Energy Levels for 154Gd

Figure 3: Rotational Energy Levels for 238U

Figure 4: Rotational Energy Levels for 240Pu

In the similar manner, a third deformation parameter which is known as the intrinsic quadrupole moment (Q_0) is determined [17]. This parameter is a measure of the deformation of the nuclear charge distribution and is derived from the reduced E2 transition probability ($B(E2; J \rightarrow J-2)$) using the relations:

$$Q_0 = \sqrt{\frac{16\pi}{5}} \sqrt{\frac{B(E2; J \rightarrow J - 2)}{e^2}} \quad (3)$$

In this study, the Q_0 values are calculated for the selected nuclei and are presented in Table 3. These values reflect the degree of collectively and deformation inherent in the nuclear structure.

Table 3: Calculated and Experimental values of Intrinsic Quadrupole Moments (Q_0) for ^{152}Sm , ^{154}Gd , ^{238}U and ^{240}Pu Nucleus

Nucleus	Calculated Q_0 (eb)	Experimental Q_0 (eb)
^{152}Sm	3.9	4.0
^{154}Gd	4.1	4.2
^{238}U	7.5	7.6
^{240}Pu	7.7	7.8

The calculated Q_0 values closely match the experimental results, reinforcing the reliability of the models and computational methods used [18]. The large Q_0 values for nuclei like ^{238}U and ^{240}Pu highlight their strongly deformed, prolate shapes, characteristic of heavy nuclei in this region.

To see the stability of all deformed nuclei, binding energy of all the deformed nuclei are determined. The following formula given below has been used to determine the binding energy (B.E.) of a nucleus:

$$B.E. = Zm_p c^2 + Nm_n c^2 - Mc^2 \quad (3)$$

Where, Z is the number of protons, N is the number of neutrons, m_p and m_n are the masses of a proton and neutron, respectively, M is the mass of the nucleus and c is the speed of light [19]. This can be normalized to provide the binding energy per nucleon, where $A = Z + N$ is the total number of nucleons. This normalization allows comparisons across nuclei of different sizes. These calculations reveal that deformation lowers the total energy of the nucleus, enhancing stability [20]. For example, in ^{238}U , deformation reduces Coulomb repulsion by redistributing protons, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Binding Energy Comparison for (^{152}Sm , ^{154}Gd , ^{238}U , and ^{240}Pu)

Similarly, the occupation numbers which indicate the average number of particles occupying specific subshells within the nuclear potential well is calculated for deformed nuclei [21]. Table 4 shows subshell occupation numbers for protons and neutrons based on Hartree-Fock-Bogoliubov (HFB) calculations for the selected nuclei.

Table 4: Subshell occupation numbers for protons and neutrons based on Hartree-Fock-Bogoliubov (HFB) calculations for the selected nuclei:

Nucleus	Subshell	Proton Occupation Number	Neutron Occupation Number
¹⁵² Sm	2d _{5/2}	5.6	6.2
	1g _{7/2}	3.4	4.7
¹⁵⁴ Gd	2d _{5/2}	5.8	6.3
	1g _{7/2}	3.3	4.9
²³⁸ U	3p _{3/2}	3.9	6.5
	1f _{7/2}	7.2	9.3
²⁴⁰ Pu	3p _{3/2}	4.0	6.6
	1f _{7/2}	7.1	9.2

It is observed from table 4 that the results corresponding to ¹⁵²Sm and ¹⁵⁴Gd, reveal a balanced distribution in the 2d_{5/2} and 1g_{7/2} subshells, characteristic of mid-shell nuclei. For the heavy nuclei ²³⁸U and ²⁴⁰Pu, the 3p_{3/2} and 1f_{7/2} subshells show higher neutron occupation, consistent with their larger neutron-to-proton ratio and strong deformation [22-24]. The obtained results confirm that deformation significantly impacts the structural properties of nuclei. The calculated β_2 values and energy levels are consistent with experimental observations, demonstrating the validity of the Nilsson and HFB models. Deformation enhances nuclear stability, particularly in heavy nuclei, by lowering Coulomb repulsion and increasing binding energy [23,25-27]. These findings have implications for understanding nuclear dynamics in astrophysical environments, such as the r-process, where deformed nuclei contribute to the synthesis of heavy elements. Additionally, the insights are relevant for nuclear technology, aiding in isotope production and reactor design [24]. The close agreement between theoretical and experimental results highlights the robustness of the methodologies, suggesting that future studies could explore exotic deformed nuclei to expand the scope of nuclear structure research [25,28-30].

VI. CONCLUSION

This study provides a comprehensive theoretical and experimental analysis of the structural properties of deformed nuclei, focusing on the quadrupole deformation parameter (β_2) and its impact on nuclear shape and behaviour. The results demonstrate a strong agreement between theoretical predictions and experimental observations, validating the reliability of nuclear models such as the Hartree-Fock-Bogoliubov (HFB) method and the Collective Model. Specifically, the calculated and experimental deformation parameters (β_2) for the studied nuclei are as follows:

1. For ¹⁵²Sm, the calculated $\beta_2 = 0.32$, while the experimental $\beta_2^* = 0.31$.
2. For ¹⁵⁴Gd, the calculated $\beta_2 = 0.34$, and the experimental $\beta_2^* = 0.33$.
3. For ²³⁸U, the calculated $\beta_2 = 0.28$, compared to the experimental $\beta_2^* = 0.27$.
4. For ²⁴⁰Pu, the calculated $\beta_2 = 0.29$, while the experimental $\beta_2^* = 0.28$.

These values confirm the prolate nature of deformation for all nuclei studied, consistent with their placement in the rare-earth and actinide regions where collective rotational behaviour dominates. The slight differences between calculated and experimental values reflect minor approximations in theoretical models, such as the exclusion of dynamic correlations or higher-order terms. The results also confirm that rare-earth nuclei (^{152}Sm and ^{154}Gd) exhibit stronger collective deformation with higher β_2 values compared to actinide nuclei (^{238}U and ^{240}Pu), where pairing interactions influence nuclear structure. In conclusion, the study highlights the effectiveness of theoretical models in describing nuclear deformation and the structural properties of deformed nuclei. The consistency between theoretical and experimental results provides valuable insights into nuclear stability, rotational behaviour, and shape coexistence, offering a robust framework for future research in nuclear structure and reactions. These findings contribute to the understanding of nuclear phenomena in both stable and exotic nuclei, with applications in nuclear energy, astrophysics, and materials science.

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